

Theoretical and Methodological Significance of Television Education

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 05 January 2022	In 2019, the SARS-CoV-2 virus from Wuhan, China, forced the introduction of new areas of education in the international arena. From this time onwards, education through TV courses became more relevant. However, the roots of tele-education go back more than half a century. The evolution of television education is also seen as the best way to increase the literacy of the country's population. The classification and development trends of educational TV programs also play an important role in this. The article analyzes the specifics of television educational programs.
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INTRODUCTION

There has been a lot of controversy about the impact of television on the minds of young people. There were concerns that it would do more harm than good to television. However, the global pandemic of the last two years has shown that television education is more beneficial in less economically viable countries. Observations and monitoring show that television education is a positive experience.

In many studies, researchers have observed how educational programs help increase children's intelligence. Surprisingly, children aged 2 to 7 years who watched several hours of training programs per day performed better on academic tests than those who did not watch television (1). However, children who spent most of their time watching cartoons were rated lower than those who watched television. That's why it's so important to keep track of what your kids are watching and show them educational programs. In the article we will consider the stages of evolutionary development of educational programs, the peculiarities of the classification of television education and the "pros" and "cons" that followed the transition of education to television.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Learning technology provides organizational, efficiency, collaboration, communication, additional support, virtual experience and many other advantages in the teaching and learning process. The cessation of traditional education, especially during the pandemic, began to contribute to the further development of educational technologies, especially television education. Learning technology involves the disciplined application of knowledge to improve teaching,

learning and performance. Teaching traditionally working classes will need to strengthen teaching skills and knowledge. Current education, which includes the use of television educational technology, can keep students as passive observers. At the same time, the "conteroller" feature disappears and the "self-study" increases. This article discusses educational technology, the evolution of technology, and the impact of educational technology on the teaching and learning process.

Educational technology is a systematic and organized process of applying modern technologies to improve the quality of education. Television education is part of the same process. This is a systematic way of conceptualizing the performance and evaluation of the learning process through the use of 'e-teaching' and traditional teaching methods. The word technology is derived from the Greek word "techno", which means desire, skill, way of knowing, rule, skill, tools, and "logos" means science.

Different countries use different terms and synonyms as educational technology, teaching equipment, AV resources and teaching technology. "Terminological differences are mainly due to the approach to technical features and the use of modern equipment. It is not their actual application in teaching, but their real pedagogical application," said Brahm Prakash Dahiya and Balkar Singh (2). According to the above two professors, the use of educational technology requires knowledge in several areas:

- Pedagogy;
- Psychology;
- Didactics;
- Informatics;

- The system of other disciplines related to information technology.

We can use educational technology in three areas:

- Technology as a teacher.
- Technology as a teaching tool.
- Technology as a tool for learning.

Over the past century, many key technologies (including digital technologies) have been introduced into education. Each of these technologies had to make evolutionary changes in teaching and learning. It's almost like that. For example, at first, small lessons were given in newspapers. The invention of radio in the early twentieth century also marked a turning point in education. However, it is not enough to say that there have been dramatic reorientations or changes in education. Radical changes in technology in education are directly related to television. As educational opportunities became more equal, television became the most convenient way to learn. Information and communication technology (ICT) refers primarily to educational technologies such as the Internet, wireless networks, mobile phones, satellite communications, and digital television (3).

In general, tele-education has its drawbacks. Although the transfer of education to television in terms of coverage is not so difficult, it does not fully cover students. Nel Glasov wrote about this in one of his works (4).

The advent of digital television and the archiving of television programs on the Internet have opened up unprecedented opportunities to turn existing knowledge into visual programs. It is important to remember that television is not just about educational programs that are broadcast in real time. Italian media researchers Fedelasio Narduchchi, Cataldo Musto, Marco de Gemmis, Pasquale Lops, and Giovanni Semeraro, in their article “Search and Classification of TV Programs,” categorize tele-education as a component of the Electronic Program Guide (EPG). separate (5). We explain this by the fact that the student has an electronic personal profile. There is another direction in the broadcasting of television programs. If decent TV programs are disappearing from traditional TV programs, then television education will need to be aired on separate frequencies. This practice can also be referred to as telecommuting classification or cataloging. For example, starting from 2020, separate TV channels for grades 1-4, 5-9 and 10-11 have been launched in Uzbekistan with the technical support of digital television. These TV channels also optimized their airtime and divided into groups. The classification of TV channels, in turn, has led to convenience. In addition, the fact that the TV channels broadcast in two languages (Uzbek and Russian) is also unique.

I think that the classification and research of television educational programs can be divided into three areas:

- Educational programs on traditional TV channels - the TV is watched by a wide audience, and the child's control is better.
- Separate special digital TV channels - this is aimed at achieving the goal by directing television to a full area.

Separate TV channels also require grouping according to age, gender, level of education, language skills.

- Full digital visual-educational demonstrations - in this case, the educational presentation is transformed into a full digital form, while retaining its visual form. Such lessons are not broadcast in real time and can be viewed at any time. This practice is widely used in international practice.

For example, Anadolu University in Turkey has The Open Education Faculty, which was established in the 1982-1983 academic year (6). Initially, education was provided through print media, and later, as time went on, radio and television were used as new educational technologies. Computer-assisted learning has been part of the system since 1993. Doctors of Anadolu University Medixa SAGLIK and Serap OZTURK describe distance education as follows (7):

- Individuals need different types of education. Since the current situation cannot meet this need, it is necessary to launch new opportunities and provide public education and free education by individuals.
- New technologies should prevent the lack of traditional educational practices.
- New models should provide opportunities for strangers to the current education system.

Kemil Alkan echoes the sentiments of Turkish professors, who believe that new opportunities should ensure equality in education for all (8). The pandemic is making television inevitable in the field of distance education. Television, which plays an important role in public communication, plays an important role in distance education with its distinctive position, presentation style and distinctive qualities. Technological developments in the field of communication can be adapted in the field of education as well as in many areas of life.

Tele-educational information transmitted over television is different from traditional teaching methods for audio-visual presentation. Explanations related to the topic and examples can be given visually, so the reader's motivation increases. Television educational programs can distract or distract a student from a particular point. But it is clear that television educational programs are becoming more and more important in our lives.

CONCLUSION

There is no denying that there are pros and cons to television education. Television is the modeling and teaching of critical thinking skills needed to engage an active, energetic audience through technological opportunities in an educational setting. In particular, as noted in the article, in the context of COVID-19, television emphasizes the importance of education. From the material and evidence presented in the article, we can draw the following conclusions:

- Television education provides a uniform education for the general public;
- Increases public literacy;

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- Bypasses regional borders and quickly becomes popular;
- Adapts to any time and technological process (eg internet systems).

Do television educational programs encourage children to be like traditional educators?

- The TV can be passive or active while watching. In this process, as we said at the beginning of our article, it is possible to turn a passive learner into an active learner under parental control.

How commercialized is television education?

- Some television educational programs may be designed to perform an expanded advertising function for goods. In this process, TTD will be able to finance the programs through passive advertising. Although this is not the case on Uzbek television, in fact it is a very convenient opportunity for advertisers.

How do television educational programs affect children emotionally?

- There is another advantage of television educational programs: it is the strength of visualization. It can easily change the emotional state of the viewer through visual effects.

It has caused a lot of controversy about the impact of television on the minds of young people. Television has shown that the global pandemic of the last two years has made television education more useful in economically weaker countries. Observations and monitoring show that television education is a positive experience. Tele-education can be a key tool in the near future.

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